

A SIMULATION MODEL FOR IMPROVING A NON-LINEAR SENSOR RESPONSE USING LINEAR SOURCE SEPARATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an empirical simulation model for the frequency response of an eddy-current sensor to a distance measurement disturbed by target temperature variations. In previous papers [3, 4], we have shown that source separation [6, 2] could be a method to obtain a good distance measurement independently from temperature variations. The linearisation of the non-linear frequency response of the sensor using a model based on a calibration curve seems not to be sufficient to always obtain good and precise enough results. The aim of the simulation model is then to represent the mean behavior of the sensor, in order to test the applicability of linear separation techniques for this problem. Hence, exploitation of experimental results permits to obtain mathematically a linear mixing of distance and temperature. We show that despite a mixing matrix close to singularity, good results can be obtained using linear BSS with simulated signals, and comparison is given between separation of real signals and simulated ones.

1 INTRODUCTION

Because of their low cost and good performances, the eddy-current sensors (ECS) are widely used in industry. They are contactless measuring devices, unaffected by dust contamination or oil projection. Indeed, temperature variations of the object to be sensed (target) or of the environment can perturb the sensor response. The aim of our experiments is to obtain a precise distance measurement between the target and our proximity ECS, despite environmental variations, especially temperature.

We showed experimentally in [3] that Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [2] can be a way to extract the temperature profile of the target from the distance measurement provided by the sensor. But the intrinsic non-linear nature of its response makes that the noise created by any imperfection on the behavior of the experimental elements and the thermal exchange that exists when only the target is warmed-up adds a non-linear, non-stationary component to the estimated

distance measurement because it follows the response curve. That often causes linear techniques of Blind Source Separation (BSS) [6] or ICA to fail. In some cases, a solution can be the use of the a priori knowledge of the temperature evolution [4]. Good results in term of estimated distance can then be obtained; but it imposes to use another sensor, giving us thermal information.

We show here how to conceive an empirical model of the sensor response, taking into account both the distance and the temperature. This model shows good precision and represents the mean behavior of the sensor, *i.e.* without all the noise sources and thermal exchanges between the sensor and the target. A simple reasoning leads directly from the non-linear expression of the sensor response to a linear combination of distance and temperature. Very good separation can be obtained with the application of linear BSS on simulated responses of our sensor. Using then the estimated temperature profile, the inter-surfaces distance that depends upon temperature because of materials thermal expansions and, thus, can not be directly obtained by BSS, can be deduced from the independent component of distance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The sensitive element of the sensor developed for our experiments is a flat spiral coil engraved on a printed circuit board [7]. In order to obtain different responses, the coil is the principal element of a set of Clapp oscillators with different central frequency. For the study presented here, the set is limited to 2 oscillators, that is sufficient for using BSS. Functioning principle relies on coil-target mutual inductance modification due to the presence of a metallic object in the magnetic field created by the coil. Hence, oscillator's frequencies f_1 and f_2 follow the gap variations between sensor and target that was chosen to be an aluminum plate. The curves representing frequency response versus distance are classically called lift-off curves and decrease exponentially as shown in figure (1). All our experiences took place in an oven, regulated in temperature and moisture, so as the plate

surface only can be warmed-up. That later is moved by a stepping motor, controlled by a PC giving us also measurements of the two oscillator frequencies, the air and plate temperature, and the humidity degree. Displacement measurements are in the $[0, 10000]\mu m$ range, and the true distance probe-target is given by a precise interferometric laser system.

At fixed ambient and plate temperatures, true measured distance permits to build reference lift-off curves (RC) providing the actual frequencies obtained on the distance interval we use. These ones are used to get a model of the sensor response, independent from temperature gradients. Hence at the reference temperature θ_{ref} , for a frequency response $f_{mes}^{\theta_{ref}}$ of an oscillator which central frequency is f_0 , a plate-sensor distance estimate is given by $\hat{d} = \Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(f_{mes}^{\theta_{ref}})$, $\Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(\cdot)$ being the reference model (parametric or eventually neuronal) obtained from the RC corresponding to that oscillator.

3 A SIMULATION MODEL FOR THE MEAN SENSOR BEHAVIOR

Considering that the only a priori knowledge is the reference model $\Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(\cdot)$, we note

$$\hat{d}^\theta = \Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(f_{mes}^\theta) \quad (1)$$

the distance estimate for a plate temperature $T_{pl} = \theta^\circ C$ different from θ_{ref} , obtained from a frequency response f_{mes}^θ . In order to make a simulation model, one must answer the following: how to compute an estimate $\hat{f}_{sim}^\theta$ of the frequency f_{mes}^θ which would have provided the sensor in response to a plate temperature $T_{pl} = \theta^\circ C$ and a distance d ?

A way to achieve this goal is to approach $\hat{d}^\theta$. When the plate does not move while it is warmed-up, two phenomena are to be taken into account: the material expansions, and the changes in the mutual inductance between the coil and the metallic target. The first leads to a difference between true distances d measured at $T_{pl} = \theta_{ref}$ and d^θ obtained at $T_{pl} = \theta$; we can write $\Delta d^\theta = d^\theta - d$. And both phenomena induce a drift in frequency between f_{mes}^θ and $f_{mes}^{\theta_{ref}}$ as shown in figure 1 for three different temperatures. This drift leads to a gap $\varepsilon^\theta = \hat{d}^\theta - d^\theta$ between the estimated and the true distance. Then, we obtain $\hat{d}^\theta$ as a function of d and of the two gaps Δd^θ and ε^θ :

$$\hat{d}^\theta = \varepsilon^\theta + \Delta d^\theta + d \quad (2)$$

A series of experiments has permit to observe the behavior of these two gaps. From these ones, we find that fitting is possible with two first order polynomials in $\Delta\theta = \theta - \theta_{ref}$, for a sufficient precision of $\pm 0.4\mu m$ and $\pm 1\mu m$ maximum in a $[3000, 10000]\mu m$ range and for the two frequencies we used respectively. Better results can be achieved by using second order, but recalling that we

Figure 1: (left) Classical lift-off curve: sensor response taken at $20^\circ C$ for a central frequency of $487kHz$. (right) Reference curves for different plate temperature (from bottom to top: $20^\circ C$, $60^\circ C$, $90^\circ C$), zoom on $[3000 - 5000]\mu m$.

want to obtain a linear behavior to the mixing for future use of source separation, we conserve the first order fitting and work on the interval defined below:

$$\Delta d^\theta + \varepsilon^\theta = a\Delta\theta + b, \quad (3)$$

and from equations 2 and 3, an approximation of $\hat{d}^\theta$ is then

$$\tilde{d} = d + a\Delta\theta + b. \quad (4)$$

The simulation model can be then easily built. With the knowledge of the reference model $\Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(\cdot)$ and the mean behavior of the sensor against temperature variations represented by equation 3, it can be defined as follows. For a distance d at $T_{pl} = \theta_{ref}$, *i.e.* independent from temperature variations, at a given plate temperature θ , the simulated sensor frequency response is obtained from eqn. (4) by $\hat{f}_{sim}^\theta = (\Pi_{f_0}^{ref})^{-1}(\tilde{d})$. To resume, the empirical simulation model function of distance and temperature gap, is:

$$\hat{f}_{sim}^\theta = f_0(1 - \beta \exp(-\alpha_1 \tilde{d} - \alpha_2 \tilde{d}^2))^{-1/2}, \quad (5)$$

with $\tilde{d} = d + a\Delta\theta + b$.

Frequencies obtained from this model match the measured ones obtained during real experiments with a few kHz of error. Concerning the estimated distance (provided by $\Pi_{f_0}^{ref}$), the previous model (5) leads to a precision of $\pm 10\mu m$ in the worst case. This is a good objective because common industrial sensors have a linearity precision of the order of 1% of the measurement range, and this model provides about 0.15%.

4 LINEAR BLIND SOURCE SEPARATION: RESULTS

4.1 Introduction

The BSS problem consists in recovering a vector of statistically independent sources $\mathbf{s}(t)$ issued from real phenomena, considering only the response of some sensors which receive a mixing of these sources, $\mathbf{x}(t)$. For being processed by ICA or linear instantaneous BSS, the mixing has to have the following general case form:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{s}(t) + \nu(t) \quad (6)$$

Figure 2: Distance and temperature profiles taken as sources, and their joint distribution.

where ν is an additive noise vector, independent with $\mathbf{s}$, that can be considered to be Gaussian. It is well known now that with a condition of independency on the unknown sources, these ones can be retrieved at best up to scaling and permutation from this type of mixing. For our problem that consists in recovering the correct distance and temperature from the response of our sensor, the only knowledge for each oscillator we use is a RC at $T_{pl} = \theta_{ref}$; that is a set of parameters $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta\}$ for a mathematical modeling or a neural network, giving a distance estimate $\hat{d}^\theta = \Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(f_{mes}^\theta)$. This estimate is correct for frequencies measured at this temperature, and for other ones, it contains informations relative to temperature as suggests the simulation model (5) that we have defined. The usual method we have used ([3, 4]) to obtain results with source separation is to calculate two or more distance estimates from the frequencies provided by different oscillators and use them as the components of the mixing vector: $\mathbf{x} = [\hat{d}_1^\theta, \dots, \hat{d}_n^\theta]^t$.

With the simulation model, each component of the mixing vector will have the form provided by equation (4). Indeed, for a given d and knowing the behavior of two oscillators against temperature, we can calculate two estimates $\tilde{d}_1$ and $\tilde{d}_2$ for a given temperature variation $\Delta\theta$, and then model (5) provides the corresponding simulated frequencies $\hat{f}_{sim,1}^\theta$ and $\hat{f}_{sim,2}^\theta$. Doing the same as for real frequencies, we have for one component of $\mathbf{x}$:

$$x_i = \Pi_{f_{0,i}}^{ref}(\hat{f}_{sim,i}^\theta) = \Pi_{f_{0,i}}^{ref}((\Pi_{f_{0,i}}^{ref})^{-1}(\tilde{d}_i)) = \tilde{d}_i. \quad (7)$$

In fact, the equality $x_i = \tilde{d}_i$ is not strict if we use a neural modelisation doing $\Pi_{f_{0,i}}^{ref}(\hat{f}_{sim,i}^\theta)$ for better precision, but it remains close to. Thereafter the application of BSS is direct because $\tilde{d}$ is a linear combination of a distance term and of the temperature gap.

4.2 Results with simulated signals

Using true central frequencies obtained experimentally, we have tested the behavior of BSS for different profiles of distance and temperature, such as sinus, square or normal distributed signals. Figures (2) and (3) show one of the signal combinations we used and joint distributions at different steps of processing. The main thing that can cause problems here is that the mixing matrix is always close to singularity as can be seen by observing figure (3), because the distance will always be the

Figure 3: Joint distributions of the simulated frequencies, of the mixings (estimated distances) and of the estimates given by BSS processing.

main source for each component of $\mathbf{x}$, and the temperature source contribution is small and very close from one oscillator to another. The mixing matrix for the simulation is

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \alpha_1 \\ 1 & \alpha_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

It seems then not even necessary to use a source separation technique since we can extract a scaled form of the second source directly because we have $x_1 - x_2 = (\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)s_2$. Using this as a reference noise, the first source can then be retrieved by a noise canceling type method [8] and even if the second one is retrieved only at a scale factor, we remain in the same indeterminacies as for source separation. That is however not our purpose here because we want to know the applicability of BSS to our problem. Besides, simulations have shown that the quality of the results given by this kind of processing decrease as the mixing get closer to singularity with small coefficients α_1 and α_2 . The special form of the mixing matrix is a special case for BSS application since singularity cause most of the existing algorithms to fail. In fact, we have to use an equivariant algorithm like EASI [1]. Because performances of the later were greatly affected by noise when we used real signals, we preferred the FASTICA algorithm [5], that gave almost always satisfactory results. Based on contrast functions derived from the maximum entropy approximations of differential entropy, it provides fast results, also independently of the mixing matrix conditioning. For the signals provided in figure (2), the joint distribution of the sources estimates shown in figure (3) proves the efficiency of the algorithm. In some other cases with different sources distributions, the algorithm seems sometimes to fall into local minima giving then bad results. But outside of these minima, the sources were also well recovered.

4.3 Results with real signals

The model is validated by observing the processing results of simulated and true sensor response. The chosen testing signals were a normal distance distribution and a periodic temperature profile. The difference between $\hat{d}_{mes} = \Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(f_{mes}^\theta)$ and $\hat{d}_{sim} = \Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(\hat{f}_{sim}^\theta)$ is in the range $\pm 10\mu m$. This shows the good behavior of the sim-

Figure 4: (Left) Mixings $\hat{d}_1$ and $\hat{d}_2$ obtained from the frequency responses. (Middle) BSS estimates for true signals. (Right) BSS estimates for simulated ones.

ulation model because the precision is of the same order as that of the modelisation $\Pi_{f_0}^{ref}(\cdot)$. We use two mixing $\hat{d}_1$ and $\hat{d}_2$, obtained for two different central frequencies, and then we perform separation on real and simulated mixings. BSS has to give very precise estimates because d^θ can not be directly estimated due to its temperature dependence. The figure 4 shows the mixing and estimates for both real and simulated signals. Separation is done in the same manner and the estimated mixing matrix is of the same form. For the real signals, the Residual Crosstalk, defined for a source s_i as

$$RCT = \frac{E(\hat{s}_i - s_i)^2}{E(s_i^2)}, \quad (9)$$

is $-8.5dB$ for T_{pl} and $-25.6dB$ for d^θ . The temperature profile is too badly restituted to permit a retrieving of d^θ ; in fact, the estimated distance match better d , with a RCT of $-31.8dB$. By taking the simulated frequencies, the RCT rise up to $-40.1dB$ for T_{pl} giving sufficient precision to obtain a very good estimate of d^θ , with a RCT of $-58.8dB$. The quality of separation can be observed on figure 5, and the joint distribution for processing of the real signals shows the underlying non linear structure that still subsists.

5 CONCLUSION

We deal here with the delicate problem of the enhancement of the measurement provided by a proximity ECS, despite temperature variations. The sensor response is a non linear function. A simple linearisation does not permit to apply linear BSS in good conditions, mainly because of the thermal transferts that exist between the sensing coil and the target when only that later is warmed-up. Hence, we have proposed the conception of an empirical model that gives good approximate of the mean behavior of the sensor. The conception of this simulation model has shown that the underlying linear form of the mixing, created by using distances estimates for a reference linearisation model of the sensor, gives a mixing matrix close to singularity. Despite this fact, the model permits to achieve very good separation with only a linear BSS algorithm, permitting also to retrieve

Figure 5: Joint distributions for (left) the sources, (middle) the independent components (ics) issued from the simulated mixing, and for (right) the ics obtained from the real mixing.

the real distance inter-surfaces that depends directly on temperature because of thermal expansions. This work provides an innovative solution to the application of BSS on the ECS response, that could be further applied directly to real signals if the sensor response could be constrained to follow its mean behavior, computed by the simulation model. It shows however the limit of linear BSS in the treated case. Indeed, at the given precision, the simulation model is very close to the real behavior, and comparison of BSS results for both shows that although they are small, the noise, non linear effects or something else, that are left aside by the simulation model, are important because they slightly decrease the results.

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